

Fixed Points of Contractive-Like Operators by a Faster Iterative Process

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Abstract : In this paper, we prove a strong convergence result using a recently introduced iterative process with contractive-like operators. This improves and generalizes corresponding results in the literature in two ways: the iterative process is faster, operators are more general. In the end, we indicate that the results can also be proved with the iterative process with error terms.

Keywords : contractive-like operator, iterative process, fixed point, strong convergence

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